

Table 1 Rate constants for the oxidation of methionine by BTMACI at 308 K

10^3 [BTMACI] mol dm ⁻³	[MTN] mol dm ⁻³	$10^3 k_{\text{obs}}$ s ⁻¹
1.0	0.05	1.07
1.0	0.10	2.26
1.0	0.20	4.61
1.0	0.40	8.92
1.0	0.80	18.0
1.0	1.00	23.1
0.8	0.20	4.75
0.6	0.20	4.55
0.4	0.20	4.66
0.2	0.20	4.49
1.0	0.40	8.97 ^a

^aContained 0.005 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile**Table 2.** Rate constants for the oxidation of MTN by BTMACI at different temperatures and the activation parameters

k_3 (dm ⁶ mol ⁻² s ⁻¹)				ΔH^*	ΔS^*	ΔG^*
298 K	308 K	318 K	328 K	(kJ mol ⁻¹)	(J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	(kJ mol ⁻¹)
3.61	7.54	16.1	31.5	56.4 ± 0.4	-46 ± 1.4	69.9 ± 0.4

Table 3. Effect of zinc chloride on the oxidation of methionine by BTMACI

[BTMACI] = 0.001 mol dm⁻³, [MTN] = 0.1 mol dm⁻³, Temp = 308 K

10^3 [ZnCl ₂]/mol dm ⁻³	3.0	4.0	5.0	6.0	10.0	20.0
$10^3 k_{\text{obs}}/s^{-1}$	2.26	3.10	3.91	4.61	7.78	16.1

Table 4. Effect of benzyltrimethylammonium chloride on the oxidation of methionine by BTMACI

[BTMACI] = 0.001 mol dm⁻³, [MTN] = 0.1 mol dm⁻³, Temp = 308 K

10^3 [BTMACI]/mol dm ⁻³	0.0	0.4	0.6	1.0	3.0	4.0
$10^3 k_{\text{obs}}/s^{-1}$	2.26	2.45	2.91	3.60	4.16	4.51

absence and in presence of different concentrations of zinc chloride. It was found that there is an initial sharp decrease in the absorbance of BTMACI followed by a regular but gradual decrease in the absorbance on adding increasing amounts of zinc chloride. This clearly showed that a strong complex (A) is formed initially which undergoes further complexation with an increase in the concentration of zinc chloride to give the complex (B). Further, the regular and gradual decrease in the absorbance indicates that the total conversion of (A) into (B) is unlikely.

From our data on the solubility of BTMACI in the absence and presence of ZnCl₂⁹ the equilibrium constant, K_1 , is found to be ca 2400 mol⁻¹ dm³. This indicates that even at the lowest concentration of zinc chloride used, almost whole of BTMACI will be in the form of complex (A). A linear increase in the rate with increase in the concentration of zinc chloride points to a further complexation. Incidentally, interhalogen compounds are known to form complexes with Lewis acids¹³ and thus, it seems that zinc chloride coordinates with ICl₂⁻.

In the complexes (A) and (B), the formal oxidation state of iodine is +1. Despite the lack of evidence for the existence of discrete I⁺ ions, its stable complexes with donors have been known for a long time^{13, 14}. The formation of positive iodine species in the sulfuric acid medium has been reported recently¹⁵. Acetic acid being a relatively poor ionizing solvent will favour the formation of ion-pairs and therefore, it is probable that complexes (A) and (B) exist as ion-pair in the solvent.

Fig. 1. UV-Vis spectra of [A] (0.0005 mol dm⁻³ BTMACI), [B] ([A] + 0.002 mol dm⁻³ ZnCl₂), [C] ([A] + 0.003 mol dm⁻³ ZnCl₂) and [D] ([A] + 0.006 mol dm⁻³ ZnCl₂) solvent glacial acetic acid temperature 300 ± 3 K.

The observed dependence on the concentration of zinc chloride indicates that the equilibrium between (A) and (B) is rapid, that the equilibrium constant, K_2 , is small and the reaction is not complete even at high concentration of $ZnCl_2$, and that only the complex (B) is reactive. The small rate-enhancing effect of BTMAC suggests that iodine monochloride is not involved in the oxidation process.

Therefore, (B) is the only reactive oxidizing species in the oxidation of alcohols. Similar oxidizing species is also proposed in the oxidation of sulfides⁸. The formation of the complex is supported by the spectral studies also. The existence of the anion $[\text{Zn}_2\text{Cl}_6]^{2-}$, in tetrahydrofuran, has been confirmed by X-ray crystallography¹⁶. Various metallic salts of $[\text{Zn}_2\text{Cl}_6]^{2-}$ are also known¹⁷.

Mechanism : The absence of any effect of the radical scavenger on the reaction rate and the failure to induce polymerization of acrylonitrile alongwith the large value of the reaction constants point against a one-electron oxidation giving rise to free radicals¹⁸.

The formation of the corresponding sulfoxide indicates that methionine is attacked at the nucleophilic sulfur site by a cationic bromine species. Thus, on the basis of the observed kinetic results and analysis of products, a mechanism involving the formation of halogenosulfonium cation in the rate-determining step is proposed (Scheme 1). Due to decomposition of the oxidant in water and its insolubility in any other suitable solvent, we were unable to study the effect of polarity, which might have given supportive evidence to our mechanism. The proposed mechanism is, however, supported by the observed negative entropy of activation. As the charge separation takes

place in the transition state, the two ends become highly solvated. This results in an immobilization of a large number of solvent molecules, reflected in the loss of entropy. Further the bimolecularity of the transition state is also in accordance with the observed negative entropy of activation.

It is of interest to compare the mode of oxidation of methionine by BTMACI with other halogen containing compounds viz. chloramine-T (CAT)¹², benzyltrimethylammonium tribromide (BTMAB)¹⁹ and *N*-bromoacetamide (NBA)¹¹. The oxidation by both CAT and NBA were studied in the presence of acid and the reactions were acid catalyzed. However, BTMACI and BTMAB are not stable in acid medium. The oxidation by CAT exhibited zero order dependence on methionine while the oxidations by BTMAB, NBA and BTMACI showed first-order dependence. All the four reactions are of first-order with respect to the oxidant. The product was corresponding sulfone in the oxidation by CAT. However, the oxidations by BTMAB, BTMACI and NBA led to the formation of the corresponding sulfoxide. The oxidation by CAT involves the rate-determining hydrolysis of $(\text{ArSO}_2\text{NH}_2\text{Cl})^+$ to give $(\text{H}_2\text{OCl})^+$ which reacts with methionine in a subsequent fast step to yield a chlorosulfonium ion which ultimately yields the corresponding sulfone. However, BTMAB, NBA and BTMACI involve the attack at the nucleophilic sulfur site by a cationic halogen species to form halogenosulfonium cation in the rate-determining step, which in fast step solvolyse to form sulfoxide. Therefore, it seems that the kinetics and mode of oxidation depends on the nature of the oxidant.

Experimental

BTMACI was prepared by the reported method¹ and its purity was checked iodometrically. The solutions of BTMACI were freshly prepared in the presence of zinc chloride. The MTN (Merck) was commercial product and used as such. Acetic acid was purified by refluxing it with acetic anhydride and chromium trioxide for nearly 6 h and then fractionated.

BTMACI is only slightly soluble in acetic acid at room temperature. However, an addition of zinc chloride renders it readily soluble in acetic acid. We found that in the absence of $ZnCl_2$, the strength of a saturated solution of BTMACI in acetic acid is $0.0005 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. An addition of $ZnCl_2$ ($0.002 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) increased the solubility of BTMACI and a saturated solution of BTMACI, under

Scheme 1

these conditions, has strength of $0.0016 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Product analysis : The product analysis was carried out under kinetic conditions. The oxidation of MTN resulted in the formation of the corresponding sulfoxide. The sulfoxide was determined by the reported method²⁰. The yield of the sulfoxide was $90 \pm 4\%$.

Stoichiometry : To determine the stoichiometry, BTMACI (0.05 mol) and MTN (0.01 mol) were made up to 100 ml in glacial acetic acid in the presence of zinc chloride (0.15 mol). The reaction was allowed to stand for *ca.* 10 h to ensure the completion of the reaction. The residual BTMACI was determined spectrophotometrically at 364 nm. Several experiments with different concentrations of MTN and BTMACI showed that the reaction exhibited 1 : 1 stoichiometry.

Kinetic measurements : The reactions were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions by maintaining a large excess of the MTN ($\times 15$ times or more) over BTMACI, at constant temperature (accuracy ± 0.1 K) and in glacial acetic acid medium. The reactions were carried out in the presence of zinc chloride ($0.003 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ unless mentioned otherwise) and were followed by monitoring the decrease in [BTMACI] spectrophotometrically at 364 nm for at least three half-lives. The pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{obs} , was evaluated from the linear ($r^2 > 0.995$) plots of $\log [\text{BTMACI}]$ against time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. The experimental third order rate constant, k_3 , was determined from the relationship : $k_3 = k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{MTN}] [\text{ZnCl}_2]$.

Spectral studies : UV-Vis spectra of $0.0005 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of BTMACI alone and in presence of 0.002 , 0.003 and $0.006 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of ZnCl_2 were recorded on a HP-diode array spectrophotometer (Model 8452A), at 300 ± 3 K using glacial acetic acid as the solvent and blank. The scanning speed was 600 nm s^{-1} .

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to University Grants Commission (India) for financial support.

References

1. S. Kajigaeshi, T. Kakinami, H. Yamasaki, T. Okamoto and S. Fujisaki, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1988, **61**, 600.

2. S. Kajigaeshi, T. Kakinami, M. Moriwaki, T. Tanaka. S. Fujisaki and T. Okamoto, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1989, **62**, 439.
3. S. Mitra and K. Sreekumar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B.* 1997, **36**, 133.
4. S. Kajigaeshi, H. Kawamuki and S. Fujisaki, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1989, **62**, 2585.
5. S. Kajigaeshi, Y. Morikawa, S. Fujisaki, T. Kakinami and K. Nishihara, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1991, **64**, 336.
6. T. Kakinami, S. Kajigaeshi, Y. Morikawa, S. Fujisaki and K. Nishihara, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1991, **64**, 1060.
7. S. K. Mehla, S. Kothari and K. K. Banerji, *Oxid. Commun.*, 2000, **23**, 229.
8. R. Sankhla and S. Kothari, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 2002, 155; (*M*) 0465.
9. A. Goyal and S. Kothari, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 2003, **76**, 01.
10. P. Gupta and S. Kothari, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 474; P. S. C. Rao, D. Suri, S. Kothari and K. K. Banerji, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 1998, 510; (*M*) 2251.
11. S. Mittal, V. Sharma and K. K. Banerji, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 1986, 264.
12. D. S. Mahadevappa, A. Ananda and N. M. M. Gowda, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1985, 39.
13. A. J. Downs and C. J. Adams, "Comprehensive Inorganic Chemistry", Vol. 2, eds. J. C. Bailar, H. J. Emeleus, R. N. Nyholm and A. F. Trotman-Dickenson, Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1973, p. 1344.
14. Supplement to Mellor's "Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", Vol. 2, eds. H. V. A. Briscoe, A. A. Eldridge and G. M. Dyson, Longmans, London, 1956, 500.
15. V. K. Chaikovski, T. S. Kharlova, V. D. Filimonov and T. A. Saryucheva, *Synthesis*, 1999, 748.
16. F. A. Cotton, S. A. Duraj, M. W. Extine, G. E. Lewis, W. J. Roth, C. D. Schmulbach and W. Schwotzer, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1983, 1377.
17. H. J. Emeleus, "Inorganic Chemistry", (MTP International Review of Science), Vol. 1, Butterworths, London, 1973, 53.
18. R. Mehnert and O. Brede, *Radiat. Phys. Chem.*, 1984, **23**, 463.
19. A. Goyal and S. Kothari, *Indian. J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2003, **42**, 2129.
20. S. Goel, S. Kothari and K. K. Banerji, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 1996, 230; (*M*) 1318.